

Women Empowerment in India through Women Entrepreneurship

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Abstract

Women entrepreneurship is the process whereby women takes the lead and organize the business or industry and provides employment to others. Entrepreneurship is the state of mind which every woman has in her mind but has not been capitalized in the way it should be. Women entrepreneurs engaged in business due to push and pull factors which encourage them to have an independent occupation and stand on their legs. A sense towards independent decision making on their life and career is the motivational factor behind this urge. Saddled with household chores and domestic responsibilities, women want to get independence. Under the influence of these factors, women entrepreneurs choose a profession as a challenge and as an urge to do something new. Women in India constitute 48% of the total nation At this juncture; effective steps are needed to provide entrepreneurial awareness, orientation and skill development programs to women. Resurgence of entrepreneurship is the need of the hour focusing on educating women strata of population, spreading awareness and consciousness amongst women to outshine in the enterprise field. In this background, this paper aims at discussing the growth, the factors influencing women entrepreneurship, the problems of women entrepreneurs in India and the suggestions for the problems hindering the growth and development of women entrepreneurship in India.

Key Words: Entrepreneurship, Women Entrepreneurship, Economic Independence, Women Empowerment

Introduction

Sakuntala Narasimhan, a Journalist quotes, “It is awareness, rather than conventional schooling or education in terms of degrees or classrooms, which makes a vital difference.” Modern age has lifted the veil of ignorance and the myth that a women’s place is in the home has been convincingly demolished. Although women’s status during Veda and Upanishad period was respectable but their position had deteriorated and even now women are seen harassed in many respects. Women were treated as property of men and any deviation from the norm was frowned upon and, if possible, immediately curbed. Our constitution gives equal status to women in relation to men and several provisions are there for their upliftment. Yet, women are not utilizing the laws properly. However, slowly and subtly, changes are creeping in. Women have been shifting to towns and cities, there is education and economic independence and doors are open giving her access to areas where she is growing and blossoming as a person in her own right. Women do have vast entrepreneurial talent which can be harnessed to convert them from the position of job seeker

to job givers. Entrepreneurship itself has been recognized as a full-fledged profession and women entrepreneurship is an even newer phenomenon in India.

Due to increase in cost of living, it has become necessary for women to undertake economic activities and support their families. They have made their mark in business for the following reasons.

- They want new challenges and opportunities for self-fulfillment
- They want to prove their mettle in innovative and competitive jobs.
- They want the change to control the balance between their family responsibilities and their business lives.

Women play a very important role in the economic development of India. They involved in business activities at all levels, making significant contributions to economic growth. Nowadays, Indian women are increasingly active in parts of the economy that were previously considered male domain..

Women Entrepreneurship: Conceptual Framework

In nutshell, women entrepreneurs are those women who think of a business enterprise, initiate it, organize it, organize and combine the factors of production, operate the enterprise and undertake risks and handle economic uncertainty involved in running a business enterprise.

Factors Responsible For Encouraging Women to Become Entrepreneurs

Employment gives status and economic independence to women leading to women empowerment.. Women set up an enterprise due to economic and non economic factors. Various important factors can be due to motivational factors and facilitating factors which are listed below.

Motivational Factors:

- (a) Economic necessity
- (j) Developing risk-taking ability
- (b) Economic independence
- (k) Employment generation
- (c) Self-actualization
- (l) Family occupation
- (d) Establishing their own creativity
- (m) Gender freedom and mobility
- (e) Establishing their own identity
- (n) Government policies and programmes
- (f) Equal status in society
- (o) Success stories of friends
- (g) Achievement excellence
- (p) Role model to others
- (h) Education and qualification
- (i) Building self confidence

Facilitating Factors

- (a) Adequate financial facilities
- (b) Innovative thinking
- (c) Self-satisfaction
- (d) Co-operation of family
- (e) Network of contracts
- (f) Experienced and skilled people at work
- (g) Support of family members

Measures for the growth and development of women entrepreneurship in India

The basic requirement in development of women entrepreneurship is to make aware the women regarding her existence, her unique identity and her contribution towards the economic growth and development of country. The following measures are suggested to empower the women to seize the various opportunities and to face challenges in business. There should be a continuous attempt to inspire, encourage, motivate and co-

operate women entrepreneurs. Attempts should be there to enhance the standards of education of women general as well making effective provisions for their training, practical experience and personality development programmes to improve their over-all personality standards. Attempts to bring about a society attitude change, generation of awareness and consciousness on the policy of self-development of women entrepreneurs. Establishing various policies to offer easy finance schemes for economically strengthening the position of women. Forming a cooperative association of women entrepreneurs to mobilize resources and pooling capital funds in order to help the women in the field of industry, trade and commerce. Offering seed capital, upliftment schemes, women entrepreneurs fund to encourage them economically To extend concessional rate facilities and schemes for women entrepreneurs to prosper in the field of enterprise.

Conclusion

It can, thus, be concluded that women in India are no longer an abla and remain confined to within four walls of house. They are participating and performing well in all spheres of activities such as academic, politics, administration, space and industry. Efforts are on at the Government and voluntary agencies levels to tap the hitherto unrecognized and unaccounted for strength of women to integrate them in the process of industrial development, more especially small scale industry development in the country This paper can be concluded by recalling the statement made by Pandit Jawarhar Lal Nehru who rightly says, “When woman moves forward, the family moves, the village moves and the nation moves.” The task of women has become more tedious and full of challenges. Empowerment gives status and economic independence to women leading to an empowered woman. Let us all make efforts to help woman rediscover her.

References

1. Aruna.R. and Sood.S.K: *Entrepreneurship Development*, Kalyani Publishers Second Revised Edition (Reprint), Ludhiana, 2010, pp-2.2 -3.6
2. Desai.Vasant: *Dynamics of Entrepreneurial Development & Publication House*, Mumbai,

- 2004, Fourth Revised Edition (Reprint), pp 119-131
3. Dhameja.S,K: *Women Entrepreneurs: opportunities, Performance and Problems*, Deep publisher
 4. Gordon E. & Natarajan. K: *Entrepreneurship Development*, Himalaya Publication House, Mumbai, Second Revised Edition
 5. Hattangadi .Dr. Vidya: *Entrepreneurship-Need of the Hour*, Himalaya Publication House, Mumbai, First Edition.